

as susceptible checks, in the summer season in the Adaptive Research Centre, Barachana, Cuttack. Three-week-old seedlings were planted in 20-m² plots at 15 × 10-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications. The BPH population was sampled from 20 hills/plot at 15-d intervals, starting from 45 d after transplanting (DT).

The BPH population did not exceed 8 individuals/hill until 60 DT; at 90 DT susceptible Ratna and Jaya had 218 and 112 BPH/hill. OR158-13-1 was highly susceptible with 198 BPH/hill. OR131-11 and OR131-13-13 had only 7.7 and 11.3 BPH/hill and yielded more than 4 t/ha (see table). □

New sources of resistance to gall midge (GM) and yellow stem borer (YSB)

N. Kulkarni, G.V.S.P. Rao, and T. Narsaiah, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Station, Warangal 506007, India

GM and YSB are serious pests of rice in the Northern Telangana region of Andhra Pradesh in both monsoon and winter seasons. We screened 97 varieties for resistance to natural infestations of YSB and GM.

Entries were planted in single 3-m-long rows; each row had 20 plants. GM incidence was recorded 50 d after transplanting; whitehead damage caused by YSB was recorded at harvest.

IET8340, IET8637, IET8797, RP1579-36-33, RP2091-272-3-4-8, RP2091-272-8-2-7, RP2434-24-1-2, Moirangpheu, Aganni, and W1263 had less than 5% GM and YSB damage. □

Screening for resistance to yellow stem borer (YSB)

N. Kulkarni, G.V.S.P. Rao, and T. Narsaiah, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Station, Warangal 506007, India

We screened 24 varieties for YSB resistance under natural infestation during 1984 kharif. Two 30-d-old

seedlings were transplanted/hill with 20 × 15-cm spacing in 3-m-long rows. TN1 was the susceptible check. Deadheart damage on 20 hills of each variety was recorded at 50 d after transplanting.

ARC5500, ARC6588, CO 18, RYT2908, W1263, ASD7, T7, RP2199-

115-2, ARC62 15, and Manoharsali scored resistant (0-5% deadhearts). RP2199-162-2 was moderately resistant (5.1-10% deadhearts). Other entries were susceptible (10.1-25% deadhearts) or highly susceptible (more than 25% deadhearts). □

Screening rice cultivars against rice whorl maggot (RWM)

M. Velusamy, D. Alice, and M. Subramanian, Rice Research Station, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India

We screened 21 varieties against RWM *Hydrellia sasakii* in the 1986 multilocation trial. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. The cross plot size was 8.325 m².

Seedlings were planted 15 cm between rows and 10 cm within rows. Affected leaves and unaffected leaves were counted from 5 random hills/plot.

At 25 d after transplanting, damage was 22-57% (see table). IR64 had 57% damage. Nineteen entries, with more than 25% damage, were considered highly susceptible. Only IR28128-45-2 and TNAUBPHR831293, with 25 and 22% damage, were classified moderately resistant. □

Varieties highly susceptible and moderately resistant to RWM. Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, 1986.

Variety	Cross combination	Leaf damage (%)
<i>Highly susceptible</i>		
IR64	IR5657-33-2-1/IR2061-465-1-5-5	57.3
ACM5	Jhona 349/IR28	56.6
IR62	ITB33/IR30/IR36	52.2
TKM9	TM7/IR8	52.1
ACM12	-	51.7
ACM11	Manila/IR8	50.7
ET7254	Triveni/CO 39	50.0
TNAUBPHR831305	T7/IR8	50.0
BG367-4 (AD 85003)	BG280-1*2/PTB33	45.5
ASD16	ADT31/CO 39	43.9
TNAU83152	PV2/IR36	42.0
KT7987	M63-83/Sarya	39.7
IET7988	N22/IR36	38.8
TNAU831520	PY2/IR36	34.8
ADT36	Triveni/IR20	36.0
ACM9	Selection from IR50	33.3
TNAUBPHR831305	T7/IR8	33.3
AS28883	TKM9/IR36	31.3
AS25370	ASDI/IRON297	29.5
<i>Moderately resistant</i>		
IR28128-45-2	IR36/IRIO154-23-3-3//IR9129-209-2-2-2-1	25.0
TNAUBPHR831293	T7/IR20	22.2

Modified seedbox screening test to identify field resistance to brown planthopper (BPH)

F.G. Medrano and E.A. Heinrichs, Entomology Department, IRRI; S. Alam and M.S. Alam, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute; Y.Y. Jackson, Brewer, Solomon

Islands; and D. Senadhira and N. Wickramasinghe, CARI, Sri Lanka

In field screening for resistance to BPH at IRRI, some varieties are resistant in the field but susceptible at early seedling stage in the greenhouse. We modified the standard seedbox screening test

BPH damage ratings of selected rice varieties in 4 countries in the standard and the modified seedbox screening tests.

Variety	Damage rating ^a												
	IRRI						Bangladesh		Solomon Islands		Sri Lanka		
	Biotype 1		Biotype 2		Biotype 3		SSST	MSST	SSST	MSST	SSST	MSST	
	SSST	MSST	SSST	MSST	SSST	MSST							
Sinna Sivappu	1.5 a	1.0 a	1.5 a	1.5 a	1.0 a	1.5 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	5.5 a	6.0 a
Kencana	6.5 bc	2.5 ab	6.0 c	1.5 a	6.0 bcd	3.0 ab	9.0 c	9.0 c	7.8 bc	6.8 de	7.5 bc	6.0 a	6.0 a
IR26	3.0 a	2.5 ab	8.5 d	8.5 c	3.5 ab	4.0 ab	8.0 c	5.0 b	8.8 c	7.0 e	7.0 ab	8.0 b	8.0 b
IR46	1.5 a	1.5 ab	8.0 d	1.5 a	4.0 bc	3.5 ab	6.0 b	5.0 b	7.0 b	3.0 b	7.5 bc	8.0 b	8.0 b
ASD7	2.0 a	1.0 a	3.5 b	1.5 a	8.5 d	8.5 c	9.0 c	9.0 c	7.5 bc	5.5 c	8.0 bc	8.5 b	8.5 b
Utri Rajapan	6.0 b	2.0 ab	7.5 cd	1.0 a	6.5 cd	4.5 ab	9.0 c	6.0 c	9.0 c	6.0 cd	7.5 bc	5.0 a	5.0 a
Triveni	8.0 cd	3.0 b	8.5 d	5.0 b	7.5 d	6.5 bc	9.0 c	6.0 c	8.0 bc	7.2 e	7.0 ab	5.5 a	5.5 a
TN1	9.0 d	9.0 c	9.0 d	9.0 c	8.0 d	9.0 c	9.0 c	9.0 c	9.0 c	9.0 f	9.0 c	8.5 b	8.5 b

^a By the SES scale 0–9: 0 = no damage, 9 = plants killed. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

(SSST) to identify field-resistant varieties in the greenhouse. Varieties in which resistance is expressed in older plants are useful because their resistance may be stable and not easily broken down by the selection of virulent biotypes.

The feeding behavior of the South Asia BPH population differs from that of Southeast Asia BPH. Some varieties that are resistant in Southeast Asia are not resistant in South Asia and vice versa. A collaborative project compared the SSST and the modified standard seedbox screening test (MSST) in tests conducted in the Philippines, Bangladesh, Solomon Islands, and Sri Lanka. Seeds of eight varieties and methods for conducting the tests were sent from IRRI. Varieties were selected on the basis of their reactions in SSST and in IRRI fields.

Sinna Sivappu was the resistant (R) check, TN1 was the susceptible (S) check. IR26 was selected as the basis for testing IR46. IR26 is S to biotype 2 in the SSST and in the field; IR46 is S in the SSST but R in the field. ASD7 is a R check for biotypes 1 and 2 and a S check for biotype 3. Kencana, Utri Rajapan, and Triveni are S in the SSST, but moderately R to R in the field.

Test insects were reared on 60- to 80-d-old TN1 plants except for biotypes 2 and 3, which were reared on Mudgo and ASD7 at IRRI.

In the commonly used SSST, 25 seeds of each variety are sown in a 60- × 45- × 7-cm seedbox in 20-cm rows with

5-cm spacing between rows. Varieties are arranged in a randomized complete block design with one row of each variety replicated four times. At 7 d after sowing (DAS), each seedling is infested with 8 to 10 2d- or 3d-instar nymphs. When plants in the S TN1 check are killed, damage is scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

The design and methods used for MSST are the same as for SSST except that each seedling was infested at 10 DAS with 3 to 5 2d- or 3d-instar nymphs. The F₁ progeny of the initially infested insects killed the S check about 28 d after initial infestation.

Kencana was moderately susceptible (MS) or S to all three biotypes in the SSST in all countries, but R in the MSST at IRRI (see table). IR46 and IR26, with the same major resistance gene (*Bph 1*), had similar reactions in the SSST at all locations. In the MSST, however, IR46 was R to biotype 2 and

the Solomon Islands population, IR26 was S. In IRRI field tests, IR46 was R to biotype 2.

Utri Rajapan and Triveni had lower damage ratings in the MSST than in the SSST at all locations. At IRRI, Utri Rajapan had a rating of 7.5 in the SSST and 1 in the MSST for biotype 2. It becomes tolerant of biotype 2 after the seedling stage in both greenhouse and field tests.

Only Utri Rajapan and Triveni showed field resistance across all locations. The lack of uniformity in Kencana and IR46 may be due to a lack of field resistance to certain populations or to some variation in the methodology used.

Utri Rajapan is being used as a donor of field resistance to BPH in breeding programs at IRRI. It also has a high tolerance for BPH and whitebacked planthopper and is resistant to rice tungro virus. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization COLD TOLERANCE

Variability in yield and yield components of normal and late-sown rice in West Bengal

S. K. B. Roy, *State Agricultural Experimental Station, Malda, West Bengal, India*

Stagnant rainwater or flash floods in Jul

and early Aug often damage the seedbed or newly transplanted seedlings. Farmers have to prepare fresh seedbed. When floodwater recedes, new seedbeds cause late transplanting in the main field.

Varieties adapted to different sowing times are needed to replace traditional